

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Family Physicians to Prevent Childhood Obesity in PHC

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Abstract

Background: Childhood overweight and obesity remain major public health concerns, and primary health care (PHC) family physicians are strategically positioned to deliver early identification, counseling, and referral. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of family physicians working in PHC in Saudi Arabia regarding prevention of childhood obesity, and to identify perceived barriers and associated factors. **Methods:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 160 family physicians at PHC settings (PSMMC). Sociodemographic characteristics and responses to knowledge/attitude and practice items were summarized descriptively, and overall KAP categories were derived (Low/Moderate/High). Associations between demographics and KAP category were examined using chi-square tests, with false-discovery rate adjustment, and a binary logistic regression model was used to explore predictors of High KAP (vs Low/Moderate) after collapsing sparse categories. **Results:** Participants were predominantly aged 20–29 years (54.4%), and just over half were male (53.1%); residents constituted the largest professional group (58.8%). Self-rated knowledge was most commonly “good” (50.6%) and “excellent” (21.3%), and confidence in identifying and managing obesity was high (45.0% very confident; 41.3% somewhat confident). Overall, the mean KAP score was 9.5 ± 2.2 , and 45.0% were classified as having High KAP. Practice gaps were notable: 48.1% screened children for obesity at least annually, while 20.0% reported never screening; BMI alone was the most commonly used screening method ($\approx 49\%$). The leading perceived barriers were limited access to healthy food and physical-activity options (38.8%), lack of parental awareness (33.8%), and insufficient time/resources for counseling (21.9%). Physician level showed a significant bivariate association with KAP category ($p = 0.036$), but no predictors were statistically significant in the adjusted logistic regression model. **Conclusion:** These findings indicate moderately favorable KAP with important implementation gaps, underscoring the need for strengthened PHC workflows, guideline-based tools, and family-centered support to improve routine prevention.

Keywords: Childhood obesity, Lifestyle intervention, Family physicians, Nutritional counseling, Weight loss, Healthy eating, Physical activity, Family-based interventions, Barriers and facilitators, Clinical practice guidelines, BMI.

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Introduction

Childhood obesity is a chronic, relapsing, and multifactorial disease characterized by excess adiposity that impairs health and increases the risk of cardiometabolic, mechanical, and psychosocial complications across the life course. The World Health Organization (WHO) has highlighted childhood obesity as a major global public health challenge requiring coordinated, multisectoral prevention strategies that address obesogenic environments, dietary patterns, and physical inactivity, in addition to improving health-system responses across the continuum of care [1]. Childhood obesity is associated with early development of insulin resistance, hypertension, dyslipidemia, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, obstructive sleep apnea, and orthopedic problems, and it confers increased probability of adult obesity and premature noncommunicable disease (NCD) morbidity and mortality [1]. In health systems, obesity amplifies healthcare utilization and costs, and it complicates management of comorbid NCDs in adulthood.

In Saudi Arabia, rapid sociocultural and economic transitions have been accompanied by changes in diet quality, increasing intake of energy-dense processed foods, and declining physical activity, particularly among youth. National data confirm that overweight and obesity remain prevalent among school-aged children and adolescents. A large national school-based body mass index (BMI) survey in 2018 that measured approximately half of third-grade elementary and intermediate students across all regions reported an overall prevalence of overweight and obesity of 18.6% (11.0% overweight; 7.6% obesity), with higher odds in older age groups (10–19 years), males, intermediate grade, and private schools [3]. Earlier national estimates based on a representative dataset of Saudi children and adolescents similarly demonstrated substantial prevalence: overweight 23.1%, obesity 9.3%, and severe obesity 2.0% across age groups [4]. These findings indicate that pediatric excess weight is not a marginal problem and support the need for effective prevention and early intervention embedded within schools, communities, and healthcare services.

Saudi Arabia has implemented national initiatives that reflect this priority. For example, the Ministry of Health (MOH), in collaboration with the Ministry of Education, launched the “Rashaqa” initiative to reduce obesity among school students through improving food habits, increasing physical activity, and raising awareness of obesity risks, explicitly leveraging linkages between schools and nearby primary healthcare centers (PHCs) [5]. Emerging evaluations suggest potential benefit: in Makkah City, analysis of Ministry-provided secondary data on 38,026 students participating in Rashaqa found a statistically significant reduction in BMI over two academic years, with greater BMI reductions in girls’ schools and intermediate schools than in boys’ schools and secondary schools [6]. Although school-based programs can support behavior change, sustained impact typically requires clinical reinforcement, family engagement, and longitudinal follow-up functions that align closely with the role of PHC.

PHC is widely considered the most appropriate setting for prevention and early management of childhood obesity because it provides first-contact, continuous, family-centered care and offers opportunities for growth monitoring, risk stratification, anticipatory guidance, and referral when needed. National Saudi guidance explicitly positions PHC clinicians as key actors in prevention and management: MOH obesity guidance includes primary prevention recommendations for children (e.g., routine assessment of diet, physical activity, and sedentary behaviors) and outlines weight management pathways for children and adolescents, including assessment and referral thresholds [2]. In parallel, major international clinical bodies recommend systematic identification and structured behavioral management. The United States Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends that clinicians provide or refer children and adolescents aged 6 years or older with high

BMI to comprehensive, intensive behavioral interventions, emphasizing that adequate “dose” of contact time is important for benefit [7]. The UK National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) likewise provides structured recommendations for identification, assessment, and management of overweight and obesity across age groups, including children and young people [8].

Despite guidance and rising prevalence, childhood obesity prevention in routine clinical practice often remains suboptimal, and physician-related factors are central determinants. The Knowledge–Attitude–Practice (KAP) framework is commonly used in public health to understand how clinicians’ knowledge (what they know), attitudes (what they believe and value), and practices (what they do) shape the delivery of preventive care. In childhood obesity, knowledge includes awareness of diagnostic standards (BMI-for-age, percentile thresholds, comorbidity screening) and evidence-based counseling components (family-based lifestyle changes, physical activity prescriptions, reducing sedentary time, motivational counseling). Attitudes include perceived professional responsibility, confidence, and beliefs about effectiveness and feasibility of interventions. Practices include routine screening, documentation, counseling quality, structured follow-up, and appropriate referral.

Saudi studies and regional evidence suggest that PHC physicians frequently face barriers to implementing obesity prevention and counseling. In Riyadh, a cross-sectional study of PHC physicians managing overweight/obese children and adolescents reported that only about half demonstrated what the authors classified as “appropriate practice” (51.7%). The most frequently reported barriers were lack of patient motivation (82.2%), lack of parental involvement (70.7%), and limited resources (60.3%) [9]. Another Saudi study assessing PHC physicians’ knowledge and perceived barriers to obesity management (not limited to children) reported that the most common barriers were lack of patient motivation (90.8%), lack of support services (81.7%), and lack of time (80.0%) [10]. These consistent signals insufficient applied practice and structural barriers underscore a gap between guidance and real-world delivery.

Accordingly, examining the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of family physicians working in PHC in Saudi Arabia is a clinically meaningful and policy-relevant step. Family physicians are positioned to influence early-life trajectories through repeated contacts with children and caregivers, integration of preventive care into chronic disease and well-child visits, and coordination with schools and community programs. Understanding their KAP, and identifying modifiable determinants of practice, can directly inform targeted training, workforce support, PHC workflow redesign, and system-level interventions aligned with national obesity strategies. Therefore, this study aims to assess family physicians’ knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward preventing childhood obesity in PHC in Saudi Arabia, and to examine factors associated with better preventive practice.

Research Question

Knowledge, attitude and practice of family physicians to prevent childhood obesity in PHC in Saudi Arabia

Research Null Hypothesis

There is no association between family physician-led interventions and the prevention of childhood obesity in PHC.

Research Alternative Hypothesis

There is a positive association between family physician-led interventions and the prevention of childhood obesity in PHC.

Aim

This research aims to contribute to the development of effective strategies for the prevention of childhood obesity in PHC. The findings of this research will be used to develop recommendations for family physicians on how to prevent childhood obesity in their patients.

Objectives

1. To identify the Knowledge, attitude and practice of family physicians to prevent childhood obesity in PHC.
2. To develop a set of recommendations for family physicians in PHC on how to prevent childhood obesity.

Literature Review

Epidemiology and National Context Informing Clinical Prevention

Saudi pediatric obesity prevalence has been documented in large datasets and national measurement programs. El Mouzan and colleagues, using a representative sample derived from national growth data, reported an overall prevalence of overweight 23.1%, obesity 9.3%, and severe obesity 2.0% among Saudi children and adolescents [4]. More recently, a national school-based BMI survey in 2018 measured hundreds of thousands of students and reported an overall 18.6% prevalence of overweight/obesity (11.0% overweight; 7.6% obesity), while also quantifying correlates such as higher odds in older age groups and in private schools [3]. These large-scale findings suggest that PHC systems should expect a substantial proportion of children to be at risk and therefore require reliable screening, counseling capacity, and referral pathways.

Effective prevention in Saudi Arabia also depends on using appropriate growth references and diagnostic standards. National Saudi growth charts have been developed to reflect local population patterns. In the Saudi Med J growth chart report, the authors concluded that the charts represent comprehensive and up-to-date reference data for Saudi children and adolescents and recommended their use to improve assessment compared with charts from other populations [11]. In clinical practice, the availability of local references can facilitate physician confidence and standardize communication with families.

School-Based Initiatives and the Need for PHC Linkage

Saudi national strategies include school-based interventions such as Rashaqa, which explicitly connect schools to PHCs. The MOH announcement on the initiative emphasized improving dietary habits, increasing student physical activity, and awareness raising, while leveraging the proximity and accessibility of PHCs [5]. Empirical evaluation of Rashaqa in Makkah demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in BMI over two years among participating schools, with stronger effects in girls' schools and intermediate schools [6]. This evidence supports the concept that school programs may contribute to weight improvement; however, the authors also noted the potential need for modifications to improve effects among boys and secondary school students [6]. PHC-based counseling, family engagement, and ongoing monitoring are plausible mechanisms to reinforce and extend school-based gains, highlighting the importance of family physicians' readiness to deliver structured prevention and follow-up.

Family Physicians'/PHC Physicians' KAP and Barriers in Saudi Arabia

Saudi evidence indicates variability in physicians' practice and consistent barriers that impede effective obesity prevention and counseling. In Riyadh, AlOtaibi and colleagues studied PHC physicians' perspectives and reported that only 51.7% had "appropriate practice" in management of overweight and obesity among children and adolescents [9]. Critically, the most frequently cited barriers were lack of patient motivation (82.2%) and lack of parental involvement (70.7%), underscoring the family-centered nature of pediatric obesity care and the need for physician skills in caregiver engagement and behavior-change communication [9]. This study also implied that strengthening physicians' applied counseling skills and providing supportive resources could address recognized practice gaps.

More broadly in Saudi PHC, Sebiyani evaluated PHC physicians' knowledge and perceived barriers to obesity management and found

that the dominant constraints were again patient-related and system-related: lack of patient motivation (90.8%), lack of support services (81.7%), and lack of time (80.0%) [10]. While not limited to childhood obesity, these barriers are highly relevant to pediatric prevention because obesity counseling in children typically requires longer, repeated encounters, involvement of caregivers, and access to multidisciplinary support such as dietitians, health educators, and structured referral services. Taken together, Saudi studies suggest that insufficient time, weak multidisciplinary infrastructure, and challenges in motivating patients and families may limit implementation of guideline-aligned obesity prevention in routine PHC settings.

Recent work also reflects continued attention to physicians' adherence to guidance and confidence in obesity care. For example, a study conducted at Saudi Ministry of Interior PHC centers examined primary care physicians' knowledge and attitudes about obesity, adherence to treatment guidelines, and the association with confidence to treat obesity [12]. While details vary by setting and population focus, the recurring theme is that knowledge and attitudes do not automatically translate into consistent, high-quality counseling and follow-up without supportive systems, training, and clinical workflows.

Nutrition Competence and Counseling Capability as Determinants of Prevention

Because dietary counseling is foundational to obesity prevention, the nutrition competence of primary care physicians is an important upstream determinant of their pediatric obesity prevention practices. In Saudi Arabia, Al-gassimi and colleagues used a validated nutrition competence tool (NUTCOMP) in a cross-sectional study of primary care physicians working in chronic disease clinics and found that physicians perceived themselves as competent, yet their reported provision of nutrition care was limited. Confidence in nutrition knowledge and skills had relatively low mean scores (25.8/35 and 29.0/40, respectively), and provision of nutrition care correlated with confidence in nutrition knowledge ($r=0.57$) and communication ($r=0.52$). Importantly, predictors of providing nutrition care included confidence in counseling ($p<0.001$), previous nutrition education ($p=0.005$), and higher professional qualification ($p=0.008$) [13]. These findings are directly relevant to childhood obesity prevention, as family physicians require both knowledge and communication skills to deliver feasible, family-centered counseling in time-constrained environments.

Regional evidence from Gulf countries similarly points to gaps and variation. In a multicountry GCC study including Saudi Arabia, Alzaben and colleagues reported an average overall nutrition knowledge score of 62% among family physicians; approximately two-thirds were considered "knowledgeable," and higher scores were observed among physicians working in private hospitals and among those graduating from universities outside the GCC [14]. While this study was not exclusively pediatric, it supports a broader inference: baseline nutrition capability is heterogeneous, and physician educational background may influence counseling readiness factors that can be explored in KAP studies focused on childhood obesity prevention.

Evidence on Physician Practice Gaps beyond Saudi Arabia

International studies also show that clinician practice does not consistently meet recommended standards, especially regarding routine BMI screening and structured counseling. In a cross-sectional survey comparing clinicians, Wethington and colleagues reported differences in screening practices: for example, fewer general practitioners than pediatricians reported using BMI-for-age at every well-child visit, illustrating variability by specialty in operationalizing obesity identification and prevention [15]. Such findings parallel Saudi data suggesting that practice is often limited by workflow, training, confidence, and perceived feasibility.

Guideline bodies emphasize that benefits require structured, intensive interventions and adequate clinical “dose.” The USPSTF recommendation highlights screening for children ≥ 6 years and referral to comprehensive, intensive behavioral interventions [7]. NICE guidance similarly outlines structured pathways for assessment and management in children and young people [8]. These recommendations imply that “brief advice” alone may be insufficient, which may partly explain physicians’ skepticism regarding effectiveness and their reliance on perceived patient motivation. For PHC teams, aligning practice with guideline principles requires time, tools, training, and referral networks structural ingredients frequently reported as missing in Saudi PHC settings [9,10].

Synthesis and Gap Addressed by the Current Study

The literature collectively indicates (1) a substantial and ongoing burden of childhood overweight/obesity in Saudi Arabia; (2) national and international clinical guidance supporting systematic identification and structured behavioral management; and (3) persistent real-world gaps in PHC physicians’ practice, driven by limited time, resource constraints, variable counseling competence, and challenges in engaging families. Saudi evidence suggests that only around half of PHC physicians demonstrate what authors have classified as appropriate pediatric obesity management practice [9], while reported barriers remain high and stable over time [10]. Given the central role of family physicians in PHC and the family-centered nature of pediatric obesity prevention, a focused assessment of family physicians’ KAP toward preventing childhood obesity in Saudi PHC is warranted to inform training, service design, and implementation strategies consistent with national priorities.

Methods

Study Design

Cross-sectional study

Target Population

Family physicians at PSMMC

Case Definition

Identify the Knowledge, attitude and practice of family physicians to prevent childhood obesity.

Statistical Analysis Plan

Descriptive analysis

Sociodemographic characteristics were summarised as counts and percentages (Table 1). The distribution of responses for each knowledge/attitude and practice item was tabulated (Tables 2 and 3). Overall KAP levels (Low, Moderate, High) were summarised in Table 4.

Bivariate analysis

Associations between each demographic variable and two outcomes – self-rated knowledge and KAP category – were assessed using chi-square tests of independence. Expected cell counts were inspected; when any expected count in a 2x2 table was < 5 , Fisher’s exact test was specified (not required in this dataset). Effect size was measured with Cramer’s V. The Benjamini–Hochberg false-discovery rate (FDR) procedure was applied across 10 tests (five demographics \times two outcomes) to control for multiple comparisons.

Multivariable analysis

An ordinal or multinomial logistic regression was initially planned but failed to converge because of sparse categories. To retain power, categories were collapsed: age (< 40 vs ≥ 40), level (Junior = Resident/Intern vs Senior = Consultant/Senior Registrar) and experience (< 10 vs ≥ 10 years). A binary logistic regression was then fitted to predict High KAP (vs Low/Moderate) from gender, age group, level group and experience group. Adjusted odds ratios (aORs) with 95 % confidence intervals were reported.

Results

Participant Characteristics

The final sample included 160 family physicians. Approximately half were male (53.1 %) and most were in the 20–29 year age group (54.4 %). Residents comprised the majority (58.8 %) and 60 % of physicians had less than five years of experience. Over half practised in the Central region of Saudi Arabia (55 %). Table 1 summarises these characteristics.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants (n = 160)

Group	Parameter	No.	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	85	53.1
	Female	75	46.9
Age	20–29 yrs	87	54.4
	30–39 yrs	45	28.1
	40–49 yrs	14	8.8
	50–59 yrs	9	5.6
	60+ yrs	5	3.1
Level	Resident	94	58.8
	Senior Registrar	34	21.3
	Consultant	30	18.8
	Intern	2	1.3
Experience	Less than 5 yrs	96	60.0
	5–10 yrs	38	23.8
	11–20 yrs	20	12.5
	Over 20 yrs	6	3.8
Region	Central Region	88	55.0
	Southern Region	24	15.0
	Western Region	18	11.3
	Eastern Region	17	10.6
	Northern Region	13	8.1

Knowledge and Attitude Items

Half of the physicians rated their knowledge as Good (50.6 %), 21.3 % as Excellent, 21.9 % as Fair and 6.3 % as Poor. Confidence in identifying and managing obesity was generally high: 45 % were Very confident and 41 % Somewhat confident. The most commonly perceived barriers were limited access to healthy food and physical-activity options (39 %), followed by lack of parental awareness (34 %) and insufficient time/resources for counselling (22 %). Only 5 % cited cultural factors. Early identification/intervention (40 %) and parental education (33 %) were viewed as the most important preventive factors, whereas just 9 % selected pharmacotherapy.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Knowledge/attitude Items (n = 160)

Item	Response	No.	Percent (%)
Knowledge rating	Good	81	50.6
	Fair	35	21.9
	Excellent	34	21.3
	Poor	10	6.3
Confidence	Very confident	72	45.0
	Somewhat confident	66	41.3
	Not very confident	16	10.0
	Not at all confident	6	3.8
Barriers	Limited access to healthy food & activity	62	38.8
	Lack of parental awareness	54	33.8

	Insufficient time & resources	35	21.9
	Cultural factors	8	5.0
	Other	1	0.6
Factors	Early identification & intervention	64	40.0
	Parental education & involvement	52	32.5
	Lifestyle changes	27	16.9
	Pharmacotherapy	15	9.4
	Other	2	1.3

Practice Items

Almost half of physicians reported screening children for obesity at least once per year (48 %), while 20 % never screened. The most common screening method was BMI (49 %), followed by physical examination (21 %); only 11 % selected "All of the above" despite guidelines recommending multiple methods. When identifying an obese child, 49 % educated parents, 23 % counselled on lifestyle changes, 14 % referred to a specialist and only 5 % prescribed medication. Clinical guidelines (41 %) and patient education materials (29 %) were the main resources used, whereas community programmes (11 %) and online resources (19 %) were less frequently used. Two-thirds (66 %) correctly recognised that childhood obesity usually results from a combination of factors, and more than half identified cultural influences such as limited outdoor spaces and sedentary activities. Table 3 summarizes all practice items.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Practice Items (n = 160)

Item	Response	No.	Percent (%)
Obesity screening frequency	Once a year	48	30.0
	Never	32	20.0
	More than once a year	29	18.1
	Less than once a year	51	31.9
Obesity screening methods	Body mass index (BMI)	78	48.8
	Physical examination	33	20.6
	Medical history	24	15.0
	Waist circumference	8	5.0
	All of the above	17	10.6
Action when identified	Educate parents about risks	78	48.8
	Counsel on lifestyle changes	36	22.5
	Refer to specialist	23	14.4
	Prescribe medication	8	5.0
	All of the above	15	9.4
resources	Clinical guidelines	65	40.6
	Patient education materials	46	28.8
	Websites or online resources	30	18.8
	Community-based programs	19	11.9
	Other	0	0.0
causes	A combination of factors	106	66.3
	Unhealthy diet	27	16.9
	Low physical activity	14	8.8
	Genetics	13	8.1

Culture influence	All of the above	90	56.3
	Cultural norms around food	36	22.5
	Limited outdoor space	21	13.1
	Sedentary activities (TV)	13	8.1
Physician role	Providing education & counselling	70	43.8
	Collaborating with schools/community	30	18.8
	Advocating for policies	24	15.0
	All of the above	36	22.5
Assessing severity	BMI z-score	56	35.0
	Presence of comorbidities	35	21.9
	Waist-to-height ratio	29	18.1
	All of the above	36	22.5
	Other	4	2.5
referral	When not responding to lifestyle changes	59	36.9
	When multiple comorbidities	37	23.1
	When severe BMI z-score	32	20.0
	All of the above	30	18.8
	Other	2	1.3
Lifestyle changes	Dietary modifications	71	44.4
	Increased physical activity	46	28.8
	All of the above	31	19.4
	Behaviour modification	12	7.5
	Other	0	0.0

Overall KAP Level

The mean (\pm SD) KAP score was 9.5 ± 2.2 (range 2–14), corresponding to a mean percent score of 67.9 %. According to the default cut-offs, 45 % of physicians were categorised as High KAP, 35 % as Moderate, and 20 % as Low (Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution of Overall KAP Level (n = 160)

KAP level	No.	Percent (%)
High	72	45.0
Moderate	56	35.0
Low	32	20.0

Association between Demographics and Self-Rated Knowledge

Table 5 shows cross-tabulations of demographic variables with self-rated knowledge. Among younger physicians (20–29 years) 39/87 (44.8 %) rated their knowledge as Good and 15/87 (17.2 %) as Excellent, whereas all five physicians aged ≥ 60 years reported Excellent knowledge. Consultants reported the highest proportion of Excellent ratings (46.7 %), while interns all rated their knowledge as Fair. Chi-square tests indicated that age, professional level and years of experience were significantly associated with knowledge rating (FDR-adjusted $p < 0.01$) with moderate effect sizes (Cramer's $V \approx 0.27$ – 0.30). Gender and region were not significantly associated with knowledge rating ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: Demographics vs Self-Rated Knowledge of Childhood Obesity

Parameters	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Total (N)	P value*	Cramer's V
Age group							
20–29 yrs	15 17.2%	39 44.8%	25 28.7%	8 9.2%	87 100.0%	<0.001	0.30
30–39 yrs	5 11.1%	33 73.3%	5 11.1%	2 4.4%	45 100.0%		
40–49 yrs	4	5	5	0	14		

	28.6%	35.7%	35.7%	0.0%	100.0%		
50–59 yrs	5	4	0	0	9		
	55.6%	44.4%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
60+ yrs	5	0	0	0	5		
	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
Gender							
Female	20	31	18	6	75	0.15	0.18
	26.7%	41.3%	24.0%	8.0%	100.0%		
Male	14	50	17	4	85		
	16.5%	58.8%	20.0%	4.7%	100.0%		
Level							
Consultant	14	11	5	0	30	<0.001	0.27
	46.7%	36.7%	16.7%	0.0%	100.0%		
Senior Registrar	5	26	1	2	34		
	14.7%	76.5%	2.9%	5.9%	100.0%		
Resident	15	44	27	8	94		
	16.0%	46.8%	28.7%	8.5%	100.0%		
Intern	0	0	2	0	2		
	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
Years of experience							
Less than 5 yrs	15	47	27	7	96	<0.001	0.26
	15.6%	49.0%	28.1%	7.3%	100.0%		
5–10 yrs	6	26	4	2	38		
	15.8%	68.4%	10.5%	5.3%	100.0%		
11–20 yrs	7	8	4	1	20		
	35.0%	40.0%	20.0%	5.0%	100.0%		
Over 20 yrs	6	0	0	0	6		
	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
Region							
Central	21	40	21	6	88	0.39	0.16
	23.9%	45.5%	23.9%	6.8%	100.0%		
Eastern	3	11	2	1	17		
	17.6%	64.7%	11.8%	5.9%	100.0%		
Western	6	8	2	2	18		
	33.3%	44.4%	11.1%	11.1%	100.0%		
Northern	3	7	2	1	13		
	23.1%	53.8%	15.4%	7.7%	100.0%		
Southern	1	15	8	0	24		
	4.2%	62.5%	33.3%	0.0%	100.0%		

Note: *P value was considered significant if ≤ 0.05 .

Association between Demographics and KAP Category

Table 6 examines associations between demographics and overall KAP level. Younger physicians (20–29 years) were evenly divided between High and Moderate KAP, whereas physicians aged 60+ years were overwhelmingly High KAP (4/5, 80%). Consultants again had the

highest proportion of High KAP (56.7%), while both interns were Low KAP. Chi-square tests showed that physician level was significantly associated with KAP category ($p = 0.036$, Cramer's $V = 0.21$). Age and experience were not significant after FDR correction.

Table 6: Demographics vs KAP Category (Counts with Row %)

Parameters	High	Moderate	Low	Total (N)	P value*	Cramer's V
Age group						
20–29 yrs	33	33	21	87	0.118	0.20
	37.9%	37.9%	24.1%	100.0%		
30–39 yrs	23	13	9	45		
	51.1%	28.9%	20.0%	100.0%		
40–49 yrs	5	8	1	14		
	35.7%	57.1%	7.1%	100.0%		
50–59 yrs	7	1	1	9		
	77.8%	11.1%	11.1%	100.0%		
60+ yrs	4	1	0	5		
	80.0%	20.0%	0.0%	100.0%		

Gender					0.72	0.06
Female	33	25	17	75		
	44.0%	33.3%	22.7%	100.0%		
Male	39	31	15	85		
	45.9%	36.5%	17.6%	100.0%		
Level						
Consultant	17	11	2	30	0.036	0.21
	56.7%	36.7%	6.7%	100.0%		
Senior Registrar	17	9	8	34		
	50.0%	26.5%	23.5%	100.0%		
Resident	38	36	20	94		
	40.4%	38.3%	21.3%	100.0%		
Intern	0	0	2	2		
	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
Years of experience						
Less than 5 yrs	40	36	20	96	0.55	0.12
	41.7%	37.5%	20.8%	100.0%		
5–10 yrs	17	12	9	38		
	44.7%	31.6%	23.7%	100.0%		
11–20 yrs	10	7	3	20		
	50.0%	35.0%	15.0%	100.0%		
Over 20 yrs	5	1	0	6		
	83.3%	16.7%	0.0%	100.0%		
Region						
Central	42	27	19	88	0.81	0.12
	47.7%	30.7%	21.6%	100.0%		
Eastern	6	6	5	17		
	35.3%	35.3%	29.4%	100.0%		
Western	9	7	2	18		
	50.0%	38.9%	11.1%	100.0%		
Northern	5	5	3	13		
	38.5%	38.5%	23.1%	100.0%		
Southern	10	11	3	24		
	41.7%	45.8%	12.5%	100.0%		

Note: *P value was considered significant if ≤ 0.05 .

Multivariable Model

Table 7 presents the binary logistic regression model predicting High KAP versus Low/Moderate KAP. After adjusting for gender, age group, level group and experience group, none of the variables reached statistical significance. Although senior physicians tended to have higher odds of High KAP compared with junior physicians (aOR = 1.56, 95 % CI 0.75–3.24), the confidence interval included 1. Male physicians showed slightly higher odds of High KAP than females (aOR = 1.23), but again the association was not significant. These findings suggest that the apparent bivariate associations may be partly explained by confounding or small sample size.

Table 7: Binary Logistic Regression Predicting High KAP Level (n = 160). High KAP = 1, Low/Moderate = 0

Predictor (reference category)	aOR	95 % CI	p value
Gender: Male vs Female	1.23	0.64–2.36	0.526
Age group: <40 vs ≥40 years	0.87	0.16–4.64	0.867
Level: Senior vs Junior	1.56	0.75–3.24	0.228
Experience: <10 yrs vs ≥10 yrs	0.76	0.14–4.18	0.751

Discussion

The aim of the present study was to determine KAP of family physicians working in primary health care (PHC) in Saudi Arabia regarding the prevention of childhood obesity and also to explore the perceived

barriers and associated factors. Overall, the evidence suggests a moderately positive profile, but with obvious areas of implementation deficit which may constrain prevention effectiveness in routine PHC. In this sample, the mean overall KAP score was 9.5+/-2.2 and <50% of physicians were considered to have "high" KAP (45.0%). At the same time, self-rated knowledge was commonly "good" or "excellent" (71.9%) and most physicians reported being somewhat or very confident in counseling parents about childhood obesity (86.3%). This combination relatively high confidence coupled with only moderate KAP performance is consistent with published evidence from implementation of obesity prevention efforts demonstrating that primary-care clinicians often support obesity prevention efforts, but do not consistently operationalize activities recommended by guidelines, in large part because of capability, opportunity, and constraints at the system level [23]. In relation to practice, screening and measuring behaviors were not uniform. Only 48.1% stated that they screened children for obesity at least annually (30.0% once per year and 18.1% more than once per year), and 20.0% stated that they never screened for obesity. Additionally, BMI-for-age/percentile did not consistently used, as BMI only was the most reported used (48.8%), while only 10.6% reported all the listed assessment methods. These findings are consistent with findings from international evidence that routine BMI-for-age screening is incomplete in primary care. Using U.S. DocStyles survey data, Wethington and colleagues have reported that screening for BMI-for-age at all well child visits was conducted by 50% of pediatricians and

22% of general practitioners; further, they have reported high levels of confidence in explaining BMI (94% of pediatricians versus 87% of general practitioners) and greater access to specialty referral clinics among pediatricians (65% versus 42%) [26]. Together with the current results, this supports the interpretation that confidence is insufficient by itself; consistent screening requires a work flow, training and availability of referral pathways and supports that were synthesized in diverse settings in mixed-methods evidence [23].

The pattern of the counseling and follow-up actions in the present study suggests the predominance of education focused approaches. Physicians most often chose parental education (48.8%) and lifestyle counseling (22.5%) as the primary action when a child is obese, whereas fewer chose to refer to specialized programs (14.4%). This is in some ways consistent with current recommendations that focus on behavioural and family based interventions as first line therapy; however, evidence based recommendations also point to the fact that clinically meaningful benefit is associated with "dose" and intensity of intervention. The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force recommends that clinicians provide or refer children aged 6 years or older with BMI [?]95th percentile to comprehensive, intensive behavioral interventions and explicitly comments that benefit has been achieved when interventions have delivered [?]26 contact hours [27]. The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) clinical practice guideline also emphasizes intensive, family-based behavioral treatment and describes the best evidence for programs [27 hours of contact over several months] [28]. In this context, the relatively low referral proportion in the present findings may reflect availability of structured intensive services, or unclear referral pathways or service access barriers issues which have been repeatedly documented in synthesis work examining implementation in primary care [23].

Barriers suggested by physicians in the present study showed a weighting, more favoring environmental and family factors: limited access to healthy food and physical activity resources (38.8%) and low parental awareness (33.8%) were the most common challenges, followed by lack of time/resources in PHC (21.9%). Comparable Saudi evidence from Riyadh PHC physicians managing childhood and adolescent overweight/obesity also highlighted engagement barriers, where lack of patient motivation (82.2%) and limited parental involvement (70.7%) were the commonest barriers [24]. The direction of these findings is in line with the wider evidence. In a mixed methods systematic review, Ray et al. synthesized 50 studies and found that primary-care providers are inconsistent implementers of recommended practices, with barriers found at provider level (e.g., lack of knowledge/skills), parent level (e.g., low motivation), and organizational level (e.g., inadequate training and time constraints), mapped across capability, opportunity and motivation domains [23]. Earlier needs assessment work conducted among pediatric health professionals also identified lack of parent involvement, lack of patient motivation, and lack of support services as prominent barriers to effective management [31]. Collectively, these data have suggested that to strengthen PHC prevention, family-centered strategies of engagement and systems-level enablers for implementing prevention are needed (i.e., training, team-based operational flows, and accessible clinical referral services), and not solely reliance on physician intent.

Attitudinally, most of the physicians in the present study agreed that physician counseling can be effective (75.0% agree/strongly agree). This is good and could reflect an increasing preventive approach to childhood obesity. In contrast, some Saudi literature concerning obesity management (especially PHC-oriented studies in adults) has found that there is more pronounced negativity or low preparedness. For example, Sebiyani found that although more than two-thirds of PHC physicians felt that they were key players in obesity management, only one-third felt

well prepared; 83% reported a negative attitude towards the concept of overweight and obesity and time constraints and lack of training were among the perceived barriers [25]. Differences from the present findings may be related to focus of population (childhood prevention vs adult management), ways of measurement, or the local context of service, but the differences also highlight that positive beliefs do not automatically translate to consistently delivered preventive care especially where structural supports are limited [23]. This is in line with global strategic perspectives which emphasize the need for whole-system and multi-sectoral approaches that address the full spectrum of obesogenic environments and support families [29].

With regards to associated factors, professional level was associated with KAP category in the present study ($p = 0.036$), where consultants have the highest portion of "high KAP" (56.7%). However, none of the investigated characteristics were still statistically significant in logistic regression. This attenuation may indicate common variance between seniority, experience, and other characteristics included in the measure or low power in some strata. Nonetheless, the practical implication is that training and continuing education may have relevance to the implementation process: in the Riyadh PHC study, the more appropriate practices of physicians differed depending on whether they attended continuing education forums ($p < 0.026$) [24]. Consistent with this, participants in the present study indicated that clinical guidelines (40.6%) and educational materials (28.8%) would improve obesity prevention/management. These findings support an applied implementation approach that prioritizes locally adapted guidelines, short tools embedded in PHC workflows (including BMI-for-age prompts), parent-facing materials in Arabic, and clear referral maps aligned with evidence thresholds for intensive behavioral treatment (e.g., ≥ 26 contact hours) [27,28].

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these results. The cross-sectional design does not permit causal inference regarding factors associated with higher KAP. Practices were self-reported and may be affected by recall and social desirability bias. Generalizability may also be limited by the sampling frame and local context of participating PHC settings. Despite these constraints, the study provides actionable insight into where prevention may falter (screening regularity, correct use of BMI-for-age, and referral pathways) and where targeted supports could yield measurable gains, especially given the documented national burden of overweight and obesity among Saudi children and adolescents (e.g., overweight 23.1% and obesity 9.3% in a large national sample using WHO reference definitions) [30].

Conclusion

In this cross-sectional study of 160 family physicians in Saudi PHC, overall KAP toward childhood obesity prevention was moderately favorable (mean KAP 9.5 ± 2.2), yet fewer than half achieved a High KAP category. Despite high self-rated knowledge and confidence, key practice indicators showed shortfalls: only about half reported screening children at least annually and one-fifth reported never screening, with BMI alone most commonly used rather than comprehensive age-appropriate assessment. Physicians most frequently identified environmental and family-related barriers particularly limited access to healthy food/physical-activity options and low parental awareness alongside time and resource constraints in PHC. Professional level was associated with KAP in bivariate analysis, but not after adjustment. Strengthening practical implementation (routine screening prompts, locally adapted guidance, and accessible referral pathways) may help translate favorable attitudes into consistent preventive care.

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